

The Representation of the 'Other' In Not Explicitly Polarised Issues in Ghana: An Approach to Critical Discourse Analysis

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Abstract

This article has been written to analyse a typical phenomenon concerning the media or politics nexus in contemporary Ghana by exploring how the processes of 'Othering' is linguistically embedded in the political discourses of the state-owned Ghanaian newspaper, the Daily Graphic newspaper, when representing the relation between the ruling and opposition political parties in Ghana since 1992. Secondly, the aim of this article was to demonstrate how Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) can be applied or broadened to alternative settings. Here, 'alternative' settings refer to contexts in which a conflict is not the topic of the discourse. As shown by the analysis, unequal power relations are reflected in political news discourses in a state-owned newspaper on not explicitly polarised issues in the politics of Ghana, which demonstrates that the scope of CDA can be broadened to include 'alternative' settings. This article was based on the theoretical framework of CDA, particularly, the textual dimension of Fairclough's three-dimensional model. Expert purposive sampling method was adopted. The work employed qualitative research design since the research relied on observation and comprehensive description that resulted in non-numerical data. The research used secondary data. Thematic analysis was employed to present and analyse the data. The data led to the accomplishment of 'The Representation of the Other' in not Polarised Issues in Ghana: An Approach to Critical Discourse Analysis.' The analysis revealed and concluded that unequal power relations were reflected in political news discourses in a state-owned newspaper on not explicitly polarised issues in the politics of Ghana, and this demonstrated that the scope of CDA can be broadened to include 'alternative' settings.

Keywords: *Other, Political Discourses, Alternative Settings, Critical Discourse Analysis, Polarised issues*

Introduction

The representation of the 'Other' in political news discourses across the world is not uncommon and extraordinary occurrence. On the contrary, beginning with at least, the latter part of the 20th century (van Dijk, 1988a), the representation of the 'Other' in political news discourse has progressively become visible, coordinated with demographic and political growths of individual countries in the world, as well as an inclination towards a more globalised world order (Stubbs and Underhill (eds.) 2006). In this circumstance, the search for exploring the weight and power of 'Other-representation' in political news discourses, being undertaken by this article, can be seen as challenging, and yet crucial in terms of generating epistemological input.

This article was written against the framework of the notion of 'Otherness' and its consequences for representation in political news discourses. This article investigated whether news discourses on a political or, in a different language, on not explicitly polarised issues, are reflective of unequal power dynamics in the politics of Ghana. One of the key concepts that penetrated through this article was the adoption of the theoretical and methodological dichotomy of *Us* and *Them* to establish these unequal power relations dynamics. In the framework of this article, the differentiation between *Us* and *Them* becomes significant in the way it empowers the objective (s) of the article was to uncover unequal power relations in political news discourses in the politics of Ghana, thus sharpening the focus of the analysis. In general, it could be argued that this conceptualisation was tailored for a dual application with critical discourse analysis (CDA), the approach

adopted in this article, since the latter too emphasise unequal power relations and regards them as maintained by discursive practices (Jørgensen and Phillips, 2002). Indeed, one way in which the authors approach to CDA diverges from the mainstream was in its shift in attention towards exploring ‘Otherness’ in ‘alternative’ contexts (alternative to the contexts usually depicted by CDA scholars). In this connection, the writers referred to the literature review of issues treated by CDA analysts over a period of time (what length?). In this case, an epitome of an ‘alternative setting,’ presented as a case study in this article, has been the representation of the ‘Other’ and in most cases, vice versa in the politics of Ghana, which have been covered extensively by Ghanaian – state-owned newspaper, the Daily Graphic. In this work, the ruling party was represented as ‘Us’ while the opposition was represented as ‘Them’. Samples of news articles adapted from Daily Graphic were analysed using Fairclough and van Dijk’s CDA approach.

The press plays vital role in democracies by providing education to the citizens. In playing this role, the press helps the citizens to interpret political messages and respond appropriately to the situations they (the citizens) find themselves. But, in Ghanaian politics, ideological biases are linguistically embedded in the written reports of the ruling political parties and which sometimes appear in the Daily Graphic newspaper thus, buttressing the assumption that the state-owned newspaper provides a viewpoint that is far free from subjective interpretation of political events in Ghana. This bias representation of political messages and other views sometimes tends to create truth in a way consistent with its basic socio-political roles.

The analysis shows that representation of the ‘Other’ in political news discourses on not explicitly polarised issues reflects a clear differentiation between *Us* and *Them* and this trend is reversed any time there is a swing of political pendulum. Instances can be drawn from January 7, 2001 and January 7, 2009 respectively when there were changes of governments in Ghana politics. This was enacted in the text through different constructions based on *negative other-presentation* and *positive self-presentation*. Hence, the negative characteristics of *Them* tend to be emphasised and fore-grounded while their positive features are usually de-emphasised and back-grounded. *Us* on the other hand, is predominantly implicitly constructed and presented in a sharp contrast to *Them*.

Based on the analysis and discussion, it was concluded that the given texts in the state-owned Daily Graphic newspaper reflect unequal power relations as well as wider structural inequalities in general, leading to the overall conclusion that unequal power relations are indeed identified in political news discourses on not explicitly polarised issues, which is the case with politics in Ghana. Furthermore, these political news discourses contribute to the reproduction of unequal power relations since they, both, report and reflect on *Us* and *Them* socio-political polarisation. Nevertheless, at the same time, it should be highlighted that the analysis also revealed that although the selected texts overwhelmingly draw on the *Us* and *Them* paradigm, some of them reflect slightly different discursive tendencies, aiming at bridging the *Us* and *Them* polarisation and emphasising solidarity and commonality, rather than difference, and negotiation and consensus rather than conflict in Ghanaian politics. Additionally, trends were detected in the political news articles which geared towards accepting the possibility of a meaningful social change and inclining towards diminishing social inequalities.

Literature Review

In relation to the case study, the authors of this article conducted a thorough research and review on issues published by two (2) journals which are bi-monthly publications: (1) Discourse & Society – from January 2009 to November 2009 and (2) Discourse Studies – from December 2008 to October 2009. Excluding book reviews, the authors examined abstracts and key words in these 2 journals so as to build a table of contents in which the authors identified the dates the articles were issued, the title of the articles, the authors and the main themes, including the methodological framework applied and the content of the analysis. The articles selected dealt directly with CDA. Again, because CDA was central to the selected article, they were categorised and

addressed in terms of type of data source and themes, while on the other hand, other articles reviewed, such as those on discourse analysis, conversation analysis and discursive psychology did not receive much and careful attention because CDA was not central in them.

Regarding the data source, the authors identified five (5) types: qualitative interviews (1); media – including television (TV) and image banks (2); internet forums (3); official – government or institutional – documents (4); and political speeches (5) For the themes, the authors identified 10. These were: (1) political campaigns (2); race, including slavery (3); gender (4); immigration/refugees (5); civil war (6); cultural conflicts (7); national identity (8); disability (9); and environment (10).

During the review of the articles, the authors noticed that five (5) of the articles carried contentious context which portrayed conflict and polarisation, based on this, the 5 articles were selected since they dealt directly with Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) of which this study was interested.

Table 1: Showing contents extracted from 2009 issues of the Discourse & Society Journal.

No	Issue	Article	Author	Themes
1	November 2009	Defending whiteness indirectly: a synthetic approach to race discourse analysis	John D. Foster	Deals with the theme of race through interviews in which white college students are stimulated to talk about race. CDA; elections and political campaign
2	May 2009	'It's not a matter of inhumanity': a critical discourse analysis of an apartment building circular on 'homeless people'	Viviane De Melo Resende	Deals with the theme of social exclusion by analysing how an apartment circular addresses the "problem" of homeless people living close to the building. CDA; misery; social apartheid and street situation.
3	March 2009	'Press 1 for English': textual and ideological networks in a newspaper debate on US language policy	Christine M. Tardy	Deals with the theme of race and immigration by analysing how newspapers portrayed a debate about changes in language policy in the United States. CDA; genre networks; inter-textuality; immigration; language policy and racism
4	January 2009	'Telling-it-like-it-is': the delegitimation of the second Palestinian Intifada in Thomas Friedman's discourse	M. Mosheer Amer	Deals with the theme of civil war, that is the conflict between the Palestinians and Israelis, by analysing how columns by Thomas Friedman in The New York Times represented the conflict. CDA; argumentation; in-group/out-group presentation

				and Israel/Palestine
5	January 2009	Inter-textuality and national identity: discourse of national conflicts in daily newspapers in the United States and China	Juan Li	Deals with the theme of national identity by analysing the two newspapers, one American and the other Chinese, about two moments of conflicts between the United States and China – the NATO bombing of the Chinese Embassy in Yugoslavia in May 1999 during the Kosovo war and the air collision between a US military warplane and a Chinese jet-fighter in April 2001. CDA; national identity; newspaper discourse and US – China conflicts

In the review of the above articles in Table 1, the authors identified that the themes were analysed in rather contentious contexts, in which there was an evident conflict or polarisation that was why they were used as examples to buttress the point in this study. Notwithstanding other three (3) articles reviewed with themes in contexts in which there were no explicit conflict, and these are shown below:

1. The article “Language and ideology: gender stereotypes of female and male artists in Taiwanese tabloids” which appeared in November 2009 edition of Discourse & Society journal, deals with the theme of gender – specifically, gender stereotypes – by examining how a gossip in a tabloid Taiwanese newspaper represented female and male artists,
2. In March 2009, the article “Entrepreneurial identities and the problematic of subjectivity in media-mediated discourses” that appeared in the Discourse & Society journal also deals with the theme of gender, but by focusing on how articles from Indian newspapers and magazines portrayed women entrepreneurs in relation to discourses of patriarchy and femininity,
3. In an article that appeared in the Discourse Studies journal in December 2008 “Visually branding the environment: climate change as a marketing opportunity” deals with the theme of the environment by analysing how the image bank Getty Images promotes its archive of “green issues” through associating it with marketing opportunities.

If the abstract of this article is assessed carefully, one could argue that the above 3 articles aimed at revealing how unequal power relations are reflected and reproduced by discourses in which a conflict is not the main theme, i.e., discourses which draw on a setting in which a polarisation was not explicit but still present. For instance, a polarisation between male and female in the first 2 articles and between an environmentalist discourse and a capitalist discourse in the third. Notwithstanding that, one could also argue that these articles belong to a “grey zone,” in other words, the way they differ from the usual approach of CDA is not easily conceptualised. Though some aspects of quantitative elements were employed in this research, the work is purely qualitative. Based on this consideration, the authors believe that the three articles which were reviewed in this study, agree with the clam that CDA could benefit from a broadening of scope by focusing on less polarised discourses. In order to crystallise the terminology in which the authors employed throughout this article, it is significant to outline that the expression ‘not explicitly polarised issues’ was used to refer to issues in which there were no evident of polarisation, dichotomy or conflict between the different competing or opposed groups, or group’s ideologies, and more significantly, in situations where polarisation, dichotomy or conflict is not the topic of the discourse or more specifically, of the text in question.

Us and Them

The case study of this article involves the examination of how a particular group (the ruling political party in Ghana politics, in particular, as influenced by the wider political/social reality in which it is embedded) has power and control over shaping the representation of the 'Other' in the country's political arena. Taking that into consideration, the samples of articles the authors analysed dealt with the representation of the 'Other,' a complex matter which has to be better conceptualised in order to be productively applied to this article. According to Hall (1997, p. 226), representation is a complex business and, especially when dealing with "difference", because it engages feelings, attitudes and emotions and mobilises fears and anxieties in the receiver, at deeper levels than one can explain in a simple, common-sense. way. There are several points to make about the way in which the representation of 'Otherness' works in texts which have more connotative or thematic meaning and, within this meaning, it is the sub-theme of "difference". He further pointed out that, although newspaper texts are very powerful, their meanings are always highly ambiguous in that they can carry more than one meaning. Because there is no one true meaning in this type of text, fixing its "floating" meanings have to be done through the work of a representational practice, which intervenes in the many potential meanings of a text in an attempt to privilege one (Hall, 1997).

Accordingly, this brings to light how people who are in any way significantly different from the majority are referred to as *Them* rather than *Us* and are frequently exposed to this binary form of representation. Such people seem to be represented through sharply opposed, polarised, binary extremes, such as: good/bad, civilised/primitive, ugly/excessively attractive, repelling-because-different/compelling-because-strange-and-exotic, and they are often required to be both things at the same time (Hall, 1997). At the broader level of how 'difference' and 'otherness' are represented in a particular political arena (such as in Ghana politics), for example, one notices similar representational practices and figures being repeated with variations from one text of representation to another.

This accumulation of meanings across different texts where one image refers to another or has its meaning altered by being "read" in the context of other images is called inter-textuality (Hall, 1980). With this in mind, the authors can explain that the whole repertoire through which 'difference' is represented at any one historical moment as a 'regime of representation' (Hall, 1997). There is also ambiguity in the messages produced by newspapers and this ambiguity is amplified whenever texts are compared with other texts, thus bringing into play the stereotypes we always notice of 'Otherness' in the press. Because of this, Hall (1997) calls stereotypical meanings as inter-textual, i.e., they have to be read "against the grain". In as much as stereotyping is seen as a signifying practice which is central to the representation of difference, there is the need to make a clear distinction between the terms 'typing' and 'stereotyping' as explained by Dyer (1982). He explained that, without the use of 'types' it would be difficult, if not impossible, to make sense of the world because we understand the world by referring individual objects, people or events in our minds to the general classificatory schemes into which, according to our culture, they fit. So, for example, we decode a flat object on legs on which we place things as a 'table' in other words, we understand 'the particular' in terms of its 'type.' in this sense, 'typing' is essential to the production of meaning.

He argued that we are always able to 'make sense' of things in terms of wider categories. In real sense, our picture of who a person 'is' is built up out of the information we accumulate from positing him or her within this different typification. In broad terms, 'a type is any simple, vivid, memorable, easily grasped and widely recognised characterisation in which a few traits are fore-grounded and change or "development" is kept to minimum' (Hall, 1997). To put it simply, stereotypes get hold of the "simple, vivid, memorable, easily grasped and widely recognised" characteristics about a person, reduce everything about the person to these traits, exaggerate and simplify them, and fix them without change or development to eternity" (Hall, 1997).

Stereotyping clearly demonstrates three basic characteristics and these are: it reduces, essentialises, naturalises and fixes; it demonstrates a strategy of ‘splitting,’ this is where there is a clear division between the normal and the accepted from the abnormal and the unacceptable; it tends to occur where there are gross inequalities of power, this is so, because power is usually directed against the subordinated or excluded group. One aspect of this power is ethnocentrism, i.e., ‘the application of the norms of one’s own culture to that of others.’ If we take the binary opposition like *Us* and *Them* into consideration, then “we are not dealing with peaceful coexistence but rather a violent hierarchy. One of the two teams governs the other or has the upper hand” (Dyer, 1982). This is what Foucault and Grasci called power/knowledge, which classifies people according to norms and constructs that excludes the *Other*, and as an aspect of the struggle for hegemony. In relation to hegemony, it is a form of power based on leadership by a group in many fields of activity at once, so that its ascendancy commands widespread consent and appears natural and inevitable. In support of this, Dyer observed that normalcy, i.e., what is acceptable as “normal”, is usually established socially with stereotypes being “one aspect of the habit of ruling groups...to attempt to fashion the whole society according to their own world view, value system, sensibility and ideology”. He continued by stating that “so right is this world view for the ruling groups that they make it appear (as it does appear to them) as ‘natural’ and ‘inevitable’ – and for everyone – and, in so far as they succeed, they establish hegemony” (Dyer, 1982)

In this way, the authors related the establishment of hegemony through managing the representation of the ‘*Other*’ in matters of ideology as pointed out by van Dijk (1998). According to him, ideologies reflect the fundamental social, economic, political or cultural interests of, and conflicts between *Us* and *Them*. In van Dijk’s approach, ideologies are considered systems which occupy a place in the symbolic field of thought and belief (cognition); they are clearly social and mostly associated with group interests, conflicts or struggles; and, finally, can be associated with language use in the way that ideologies are typically expressed and reproduced in and through language. Or, as Fairclough puts it, “ideologies are representations of aspects of the world which can be shown to contribute to establishing, maintaining and changing social relations of power, domination and exploitation” (van Dijk, 2000b). In this way, discourse is needed and used by different social groups in the contexts of acquisition, argumentation, ideological conflict and persuasion as well as those of conveying ideologies to *other in-group members* defending them against or concealing them from *out-group members*. This therefore shows that the investigation of how *Us* and *Them* as a social group, is represented can be revealing about the ideological conflicts between the two categories.

With regards to the analysis of the representation of *Us* and *Them*, the social identity theory suggests that society is hierarchically structured into different social groups that stand in power and status relations to one another and this social categories provide members with a social identity; the categorization of people into groups involves self-concept and in-group bias as a result of motivation to enhance one’s self-esteem through social comparisons; this is achieved by making the *in-group* positively distinctive from the *out-group* (Oktar 2001). Therefore, there is a tendency towards employing the contextual strategy of *positive self-presentation* and *negative-other-presentation*. Put bluntly, people are generally inclined to hold favourable ideas about the groups to which they belong, which motivates them to describe group’s characteristics positively and emphasize positive traits as typical for their own group, but to depict the negative traits as typical for the other group (Oktar, 2001). In line with these, van Dijk (1998, p. 33) presents four points which are made up of the strategies used for the construction of the discourse for ideological communication (the ‘ideological square’). These include emphasising *our* good properties/actions; emphasising *their* bad properties/actions; mitigating *our* bad properties/actions; and mitigating *their* good properties/actions. It is important to state that these presentations are not focused on participants as individuals, but participants as social groups.

Turning to the role of the media in the operation of ideology, if we conceive of ideology as ways in which the meaning conveyed by symbolic forms serves to establish and sustain relations of power and domination, then, mass communication has considerable consequences for the propagation and diffusion of ideological phenomenon (Thompson, 1990). In order to highlight the linguistic and discursive nature of media

power, Fairclough suggests that we turn to the analysis of media language. The focus is then, upon how events, situations and people are represented in media texts, which are considered to constitute versions of reality through choices of representational processes at various levels in the production of texts depending on social positions, interests and objectives of those who produce them (Oktar, 2001).

The Aims of Critical Discourse Analysis

The starting point for critical discourse analysis (CDA) is social issues and problems, and indeed any type of semiotic material (semiotic is a meaning-making process through language, body language, visual images or any other way of signifying), but does not begin with texts and interactions. It begins with issues which preoccupy sociologists, or political scientists, or educationalists. Therefore, CDA is inherently interdisciplinary, opening a dialogue between disciplines concerned with linguistic and semiotic analysis (including discourse analysis) and disciplines concerned with theorizing and researching social processes and social change (Fairclough, 1993). CDA is not just concerned with analysis but critical in three aspects. First, it seeks to discern connections between language and other elements in social life which are often opaque - such as how language figures within social relations of power and domination; how language works ideologically; the negotiation of personal and social identities, pervasively problematical through changes in social life – in its linguistic and semiotic aspect. Secondly, it is committed to progressive social change, that is, it has an emancipator “knowledge interest” (Fairclough, 1993). For instance, an analysis of language in the neo-liberal global order would focus on how language figures in resistance to the detrimental effects of the new order (such as widening of the gap between the rich and the poor or the causing of huge environmental damage). Thirdly, it also includes an assessment from a language perspective of possibilities and strategies for strengthening and broadening struggles against these effects (Fairclough, 1998).

Discourse

The concept of discourse is generally used to refer to the treatment of a subject in writing or speaking, but with CDA, discourse takes on an additional meaning where one can distinguish between many different discourses. For example, Marxist discourse, feminist discourse and medical discourse, just to mention a few. According to Fairclough (2003b, pp. 3-4), discourses are social and cultural processes that are actively shaping social structures while in the other way round (the discourse themselves are) being shaped by them (social and cultural structures). Thus, a particular discourse contains within it a corresponding set of values. It is also believed that within a certain “order of discourse”, some discourses are in the ascendancy while others are not and those who use these dominant discourses generally try to maintain the status quo once they have obtained this dominance (Jørgensen and Phillips: 2002). The “order of discourse” refers to the sum of all genres and discourses that have been used in a social context or situation, in other words, it is all discourse types within a social institution or field. It is also a kind of system that forms and is formed by specific instances of language usage (Jørgensen and Phillips: 2002).

CDA is a theoretical and methodological instrument that enables the user to investigate how discourse, social and cultural development are interrelated. As suggested by Fairclough’s CDA framework, any communicative event, i.e., an instance of language use, should be analysed in terms of the discursive practice (text production and consumption), the text (linguistic and inter-textual analysis) and in terms of the wider socio-cultural practice (the political, economic and cultural settings the communicative event is a part of). To this end, Fairclough emphasises the dialectical interplay of social practices, discursive practices and their influence on a particular text. According to that perspective, discourses are both constituted and constitutive of the social world, thus text analysis can illuminate systems of knowledge (representation or hegemony), social identity (identity and group formations) and social relations (links of equivalence or difference).

Table 2: Fairclough's Three-dimensional Model

Fairclough's three-dimensional model illustrated in Table 2 above is an analytical framework for empirical research on communication and society and all three-dimensions should be covered in a specific discourse analysis of a communicative event. His framework has some points of convergence with the work of another important CDA theorist, the Dutch scholar, Teun A. van Dijk. van Dijk has long been a leading theorist and advocate of discourse analysis as an interdisciplinary approach to the analysis of texts in social context (Bell and Garrett: 1980). Even when a different terminology is applied, van Dijk's approach to CDA still has critical points of convergence with Fairclough's approach, especially when textual analysis is linked to the "broader" dimensions of social reality. Accordingly, he differentiates between two levels of analysis, namely: "micro" and "macro" structures of discourse. On the micro level, one analyses language use, discourse, verbal interaction and communication while on the macro level, power, dominance and inequality between social groups are typical terms to be analysed. Hence, in his view, one of the main functions of CDA is to theoretically bridge the "gap" between the "micro" and "macro" structures of discourse (van Dijk, 2001). It is also important to note that in a series of studies, van Dijk developed a framework in which he applied his conception of CDA in analysing news, especially in newspapers, as discourse.

The Media

Van Dijk's analysis of practices of news production and news comprehension has an emphasis on process of social cognition, i.e. how cognitive "models" and "schemata" shape production and comprehension. Basically, his main motivation for linking news texts to context is to show in detail how social relationships and processes, e.g., the reproduction of racism, are accomplished in a micro-level through routine practices. His framework actually analyses news texts based on what he calls the 'the structure of news', processes of news production and processes of news comprehension. (Fairclough, 1995a), which aims to show relationships between texts, production processes and comprehension processes, and between these and the wider social practices they are embedded within. These works constitute another point of convergence between van Dijk and Fairclough, especially in relation to the latter's conception of media discourse.

To Fairclough (1995a), media texts provide an interesting field of study as the mass media has gained a significant and influential status within contemporary society. Thus, according to him, any media text or communicative event constitute "sensitive barometers of socio-cultural change, and they should be seen as valuable material for researching change." Although Fairclough's general framework of CDA has to be applied

when analysing media texts, it is important to note that, communicative events in the order of media discourse differ from other types of communicative events. First, he points out that media communicative events are marked by three things, namely: temporal, spatial and cultural disjunction, and second, one-way communication processes which mainly constitute media discourse; thus, media discourse can be defined as “mediated quasi-interaction” (Thompson, 1990).

This feature of the media raises the question of access and power relations. Who actually has the possibility to use the media as a field of representation and expression? According to Fairclough, the media industry is a highly elite field, dominated by those who have economic, cultural or political power (Fairclough 1995a). Due to this limited access, media texts tend to represent the world according to the status quo while the marginalised views hardly enter the discourse. To this end, the media discourse can often be regarded as ideological, taking into consideration Fairclough’s conceptualisation of ideology as “meaning in the service of power” (Fairclough, 1995a). Interestingly, the ideological elements of a specific media communicative event often arise from other pre-constructed texts and sources. This conception leads up to Fairclough’s understanding of a chain of communicative events, as most discourses presented in the media have been developed through different stages, and these transformations can result from internal institutional practices, i.e., set of institutional routines within a newspaper, example, like editorial procedures or from re-contextualisation of source-media/editorial texts or messages. In this way, Fairclough’s understanding of the media constitutes a useful perspective to guide the authors analysis, however, the point to which the authors want to draw attention is the dialogical conception of discourse, pointed by him as “a form of social practice which both constitute the social world and is constituted by other social practices”. The assumption that discourse exists in dialogue with society and that “language simultaneously reflects reality (‘the way things are’) and constructs (‘construes’) it to be in a certain way” (Richardson: 2007, p. 26) is one of the general principles of CDA. It is drawing on this assumption that the authors analysis will focus on the textual dimension; and will examine the power struggle in which CDA is interested as being reflected and constructed in the text.

In order to justify the choice of an analytical framework based on Fairclough’s dimension textual analysis, there are two points that the authors need to clarify. One, the adoption of the analytical framework proposed by Fairclough is consistent with the central aim of this article, i.e., to engage critically with the discipline of CDA in order to propose a different application of its tools. The authors argue that, this choice is consistent with the aim because in order to review the usual practices of CDA and propose a different application, it is necessary to remain within its ‘mainstream’ lines and work with tools that are generally accepted by researchers working in the field. In this way, the choice for any alternative approaches could minimise the strength of the authors claim. Thus, the fact that Fairclough is considered to be one of the main theorists of CDA and represents one of the main lines of the field makes his analytical framework relevant to the context of this article. Two, although the authors acknowledge the importance of the three-dimensions of Fairclough’s model and sustain that the analysis of all of them is necessary for a complete critical discourse analysis, the authors also have to consider that Fairclough admits the separation of the three-dimensions for analytical purposes. He also points to textual analysis as his preferred method “to capture socio-cultural processes in the course of their occurrence (Fairclough: 1995b, p. 186) and as a means to develop and spread “critical awareness of language as a factor of domination.” Also, in the course of this article, the authors had to recognise the impossibility of isolating the three-dimensions, meaning that textual analysis has raised issues related especially to social practices.

Another point to be made in favour of textual analysis has to do with the main argument of this article. When the authors decided to focus their argument on issues in which there is no explicit polarisation (in other words, no explicit social problem), they began the article from a different starting point than the one adopted by traditional researchers in the field of CDA. That is, while CDA traditionally has its point of departure in the recognition of a social problem and then moves to the analysis of discourses related to that problem, this article

has its point of departure in the analysis of discourses about issues in which there seems to be no social problem; and it was through the analysis that uncovers the presence of a social problem.

Methodology

To epitomise the authors argument that CDA could be used to capture conflict/negotiation in 'alternative' settings, a range of state-owned Daily Graphic newspaper's political news articles on the representation of the 'Other' in Ghanaian politics was selected through *expert purposive sampling*. First, the time-frame within which the articles were published was specified and concretised to limit the scope of the analysis, hence, the sample of the articles on the representation of the 'Other' embraces some periods from 2005 to 2010, basically involving two different ruling political parties in Ghana. Second, articles which primarily engulfed political-related information, such as accounts of political parties' internal structures and congresses to select electable candidates in elections, were ignored, since such type of data did not deal with the representation of the 'Other,' and it is also not central to the article. At this point, the authors had ten (10) articles. Finally, given the focus of the article, the authors conducted sampling based on a thematic approach in order to exhibit the inter-textual dimension in the analysis. Thus, articles were selected on the basis of a specific theme, their reflection about the undercurrent tendencies of the representation of the 'Other' by political leaders and actors in a daily newspaper. Articles which were left aside dealt mostly with providing the readers with background and contextualising information on Ghana, such as history, sports and political figures, and as a result of this process, six (6) articles were eventually selected for analysis and discussion.

In order to build a coherent connection between the theories that the authors used in discussing and reviewing, and the analytical strategy that was applied in the analysis of the Daily Graphic newspaper articles, the authors adopted two (2) main lines of inquiry. These lines are: the authors examined the texts by looking at them in terms of how the three aspects of meaning (action, representation and identification) are realised in the various features of the texts and by asking which genres, discourses and styles are drawn upon and how they are articulated together in the text, and also examined the texts in terms of the representation of the 'Other' and the ideological square, and how the various features of the text contribute to build a polarisation through the contextual strategy of *positive self-presentation* and *negative other-presentation*.

Rhetorical Tropes

Journalism is an argumentative discourse genre in which a report "should aim to persuade the audience that his or her description and interpretation is the rational and appropriate one" (Richardson: 2007, p, 64). One of the rhetorical strategies journalists may apply in an attempt to persuade their audience rests on the use of rhetorical tropes. A trope is a deviation from the principal signification of a word. He points to some specific tropes as being the most common in journalist discourse, and these are: hyperbole, metaphor, metonym, neologism and puns. Metaphors were significant in the context of the samples selected. Metaphor is a concept which involves perceiving one thing in terms of another. Metaphorical framework can be employed to hide true negative aspects of an event or process.

Analysis and Discussion

This section analyses the six (6) selected news articles published by the state-owned Daily Graphic newspaper on the representation of the 'Other' in Ghanaian politics with the purpose of epitomising the authors approach to CDA. Also, to look at the ideological struggle and power relations that govern the production of political texts in news articles and analyse the variety of texts on the representation of the 'Other' in Ghanaian politics based on a multi-dimensional approach of CDA. This analysis, therefore was concerned with the different use of discourse resources in an ideological charged frontal clash between two (2) different political parties – New Patriotic Party (NPP) and National Democratic Congress (NDC) – visions of the world in Ghana. Political discourse, according to Chilton (2004, p. 200) is the use of language in ways that humans, being

political animals, tend to recognise as “political.” This is because since 1992, these two political parties have been engaged in a linguistic war with far more undercurrent tendencies than physical confrontations. And because politics involves reconciling differences through discussion and persuasion, thus making communication central to politics both political parties (NPP and NDC) have effectively recruited different discursive practices and used by both parties to make “language” more effective in influencing the decisions taken by each party and one of these practices is inter-textuality, whereby different genres, discourses and voices are mixed or combined in a political text. This combination, as this analysis and discussion were used as a strategy to produce effective political discourse, although, combination of different genres and discourses marks off social practices and ideologies and voice is an indication of who the participants of the discourses are and what identity they assume.

The authors analysed the practice of inter-textuality in texts related to the representation of the ‘Other’. Inter-textuality, both vertical and horizontal were highlighted in an attempt to explore the ideological interactions manifested through the use of prior texts in new ones. Two discourses of two political actors (from the two leading political parties in Ghana – NPP and NDC, who have taken turns to wrestle power from another and rule Ghana since 1992) formed the core of the discussion. The analysis concentrated on how political discourses on the representation of the ‘Other’ is enacted in texts in newspaper articles by these political actors. The assumptions of purpose, code of behaviour and audience (Chouliaraki & Fairclough, 1999) were highlighted in the analysis. The following questions relating to these aspects were derived from van Dijk's (2003) heuristics method of ideology and were answered in the analysis with examples: *purpose* – why were the political actors saying what they said? What did they want to achieve politically? What did they have politically that others did not? *Code of behaviour* – which political actor was speaking? What was the political actor doing? *Audience* – who was the political actor speaking to? Who were the political actor’s “enemies” on the political platform? A point to note is that although all the texts in the news articles the authors analysed in detail were spoken by politicians, it was through the authorial voices of state journalists/reporters of the Daily Graphic newspaper that the political news articles appeared for consumption. Simply put, the politicians are the originators of the news, but the journalists animated them in news articles. Below were the six (6) news articles analysed and discussed.

Table 3: The 6 Political News Articles published by the State-owned Daily Graphic Newspaper in Ghana which the authors analysed and discussed:

No	Issue	News Article	Newspaper	Reporter
1	November 30, 2004	Reject NDC to avoid constitutional crisis - Solomon	Daily Graphic	Ransford Tetteh
2	September 22, 2006	Celebration of 50 th Independence Anniversary US\$20 million NOT FOR MERRY MAKING! CHIEF OF STAFF DECLARES	Daily Graphic	Timothy Gobah
3	March 19, 2005	Unsavory remarks about Presidency: IT'S TOTALLY UNACCEPTABLE say Prez. Kufuor	Daily Graphic	Nehemia Owusu Achiaw
4	May 13, 2010	5 To refund GHcedis 94,080	Daily Graphic	Timothy Gobah
5	June 7, 2010	Mills's govt saves GHcedis million annually	Daily Graphic	Timothy Gobah
6	August 28, 2010	STX deal expected to create 40,000 jobs	Daily Graphic	Mary Mensah

News Article 1: Reject NDC to avoid constitutional crisis – Solomon. (Daily Graphic, Tuesday, November 30, 2004, p. 17)

The purpose of this interview by the First Vice-Chairman and the Greater Accra Campaign Manager of the ruling NPP was to make the Ghanaian electorate aware, explicitly, of the intentions of the former President Jerry John Rawlings. He believed that in unlikely event of the opposition NDC Presidential candidate, Prof. Mills winning power from the ruling President Kufuor of the NPP, Ex-President Rawlings might come back. For instance, “it has been confirmed by former President Rawlings in his statements that if NDC won the December polls, he is coming back.” He also used the interview to highlight on what would happen if it indeed Ghanaians voted for the opposition NDC. “Prof. Mills would not be in charge of affairs because Rawlings will be controlling affairs from behind the scenes thereby “making the country to have de facto and de jure presidents in former President Rawlings and Prof. Mills”, hence creating constitutional crisis or conflict”. Here again, we see politicians applying discursive influence of spinning based on communicative symbols to manipulate the voters. So, the reason for employing this mechanism eight (8) days to both parliamentary and presidential elections by a leading political actor of the ruling NPP was to reach out to the Ghanaian electorate in order to sway them to vote massively and boost the re-election of President Kufuor and for the NPP. This worked because President Kufuor was re-elected and his party NPP won majority in both elections too. This manipulation is acceptable and justifiable based on the NPP’s ideological stance. Manipulation in politics does not only involve power it also encompasses abuse of power by incumbent presidents, prime ministers and ruling parties, i.e., domination through exercising a form of illegitimate influence by means of discourse and through the voters’ fear.

Explicitly, the campaign strategy adopted by Mr. Solomon was seen by the opposition NDC as a smear campaign for domination and hegemony through the use of illegitimate strategy (manipulation), for instance: “if the NDC won the December polls, he is coming back” because he knows the former president used the expression metaphorically in order to win vote for his party, the NPP. But he typically emphasised on the preferred agent of attack on the opposition NDC using the former president as a focal point, i.e., a model that is consistent with the ruling NPP’s strategy of *negative other-presentation* of the opposition. Thus, he makes sure that truthful information about the opposition NDC, such as what former president (Rawlings) had on several occasions made clear during forums and seminars that he is not interested taking power again is not given to the electorates but only misguided or biased knowledge, as in the above, are given to the electorate. Notwithstanding, he used a good political strategy that any political party aspiring to win power or entrenched itself democratically through elections, will do in a political setting.

News Article 2: “Celebration of 50th Independence Anniversary US\$20m NOT FOR MERRY-MAKING: Chief of Staff declares.” (Daily Graphic, Friday, September 22, 2006, p: 1 and 3.

On Thursday 21 September, 2006, at a press briefing on the 50th independence anniversary celebrations of Ghana in Accra, the Chief of Staff and Minister for Presidential Affairs, Mr. Kwadwo Mpiani under President Kufuor’s government, made the above comment on the US\$20 million allocation for the celebration and a state journalist, Timothy Gobah, wrote the press briefing as a news article which appeared in the Daily Graphic with the headlines as indicated above. Mr. Mpiani was the Chairman of the National Planning Committee for 50th Independence Anniversary. He explained that the US\$20 million allocated for the celebration would be invested in monuments such as, building of jubilee parks across the then ten (10) regions of the country and rehabilitation and renewal of core infrastructure, particularly, historical monuments like Dr. Nkrumah’s Park, the building of new presidential office (Jubilee House) and completion of the abandoned Job 600 – a structure started by Dr. Nkrumah in the 1960s as offices for parliamentarians in pursuit of their work. He explained that anniversaries and special occasions provide opportunities for countries to regenerate and modernise their infrastructures. To support his argument, he quoted three examples to illustrate his views that: “During the

Jubilee Year of the Queen in the United Kingdom (UK), a new underground rail line ‘Jubilee Line’ was built to make travel in London easier for commuters”. Further, he continued that “In the Millennium Year, special projects were undertaken all around the UK and in London.” Thirdly, he quoted that, “Germany, although, had excellent infrastructures, it seized the opportunity of hosting the last World Cup to undertake a wholesale regeneration of the infrastructure of the country.” So, he does not understand why the allocated amount for these celebrations should raise a lot of noise and taken a partisan shape, making it appear as if the money is to be used for merry-making. He added that “We have tried not to make the celebration partisan but a national one which will encompass all.” This comment presupposes that the celebration has taken partisan shape and this is based on the fact that in the planning stages, the National Planning Committee failed to invite the opposition on the committee or asked for their input for celebrations with a national dimension.

Quotation is usually resorted to in most cases in order to substantiate a “*proposition*” made by the text producer. Although it is used in the academic context to add objectivity and avoid plagiarism, it can still be used as an ideologically-charged-discursive practice. The choice of using quotation by Mr. Mpiani is intentional because it is risky for him to say things directly as his own, in that, giving negative comments with implied accusation of the opposition would be seen as a sort of verbal attack and by commenting on or accusing the opposition of its criticisms, he also run the risk of being seen as aggressive and offensive, therefore he ‘borrows’ a voice from the opposition figure whom he is attacking Gadavani (2002). Gadavini (2002) explains a speaker shift responsibility of blame from himself by adopting the ‘other’s’ voice.

Although Mpiani achieved his aim, Rojo (1993, pp. 43-80) describes this practice as creating a “moral ambivalence,” because some of his audience see the quotations as a deliberate provocative reference and representation of the *Other* in a negative way. Moreso, it was made at a time in Ghana’s political history when there was the need for the ruling NPP government to foster oneness and togetherness among Ghanaians by making the planning of the 50th Independence anniversary celebration a holistic national event by inviting the opposition party and making it part of the planning processes instead making it partisan. Notwithstanding, for the purposes of representing the opposition NDC as *negative othering*, Mpiani was spot on. And for his discourse community, the quotations were what they needed to hear, read and appreciate so as to demonstrate and reinforce the unequal power relations between the ruling NPP and the opposition NDC.

Based on the above, the question is why did Mr. Mpiani quote those instances in his press briefing? The answer is, although to “quote” can either be a *verb or noun*, he chooses the *verb form* to list the above three examples in order to support what he is saying to his audience so as to appeal favourable to the emotions of his audience and their understanding logic and implicitly represent the *Other* negatively. Also, quoting others makes him seem neutral and objective before his audience, hence giving the impression that he is talking about those things as a fact when in fact, he is intentionally conveying ideological message of the NPP. Therefore, this kind of inter-textuality is never innocent politically, because it hides implicitly ideological meanings. It is a strategy used by Mpiani to save the face of the ruling NPP government by absorbing them from the proposition made originally in other news articles by the opposition NDC concerning the celebrations. He believes that through the combination of the audience feelings, emotions and politics in his discourse, he is drawing on *Us and Them* discourse unequal power relations between the two parties. Hence, it could be argued here that the text reports on wider social inequalities based on the media resources available to the ruling NPP government (as it happens any time there is a swing of political pendulum) and also draws upon the ideological square, depicting the opposition NDC as *outsiders* who needs to be excluded from the planning of the 50th Independence anniversary celebration, thus he believes he is performing his domestic political and ideological functions.

The word “partisan” used in the press briefing was used later by the opposition to criticize his expression and examples given to illustrate his point during the press briefing. Although, this inter-textuality

was observed in many other news articles related to the preparation towards the 50th independence anniversary celebration, in terms of constitutive inter-textuality, this creates some sort of ambivalence to the open-minded audience who is not aware of the original use of the expression in Ghana's political discourse. An example is taken from a paragraph in the press briefing: "We have tried not to make the celebration partisan but a national one which will encompass all." In the example given, no marks of manifestation are used although his use of "partisan" is part of a new discourse, creating more subtlety to the open-minded Ghanaian audience and a lot of excitement to the entire Ghanaian discourse community, notwithstanding, but the sarcastic tone of the use of that expression is evident, and understanding that particular expression too, is not a problem for members or audience of his political discourse community.

He uses the *noun* "merry-making" significantly to interact with the Ghanaian audience and further his political agenda. His usage of the word is done skilfully and implicitly, as he succeeded in removing or disassociating his party in power (NPP) from the comments being made by the opposition that the allocated US\$20 million is for merry-making by the members of NPP. Here, the emphasis on *positive self-presentation* and *negative other-presentation* is also reflected in the order of the paragraphs in the text and this could be related to Richardson's understanding of media discourses as constitutive of certain social categories, by among others, choosing to "foreground ones' social category over the other equally accurate alternative" (2007, p. 49). Moreover, this could also be related to Halliday's perception of "actional processes" (which encapsulates both verbal and material processes) according to which, the *negative other-presentation* can be indicate by a display of what *They* are doing with direct negative effect on *Us*, in this case, it could be argued that the prospect of the opposition to convince Ghanaians that the allocated money is for merry-making endangers *our* responsibility as the ruling party to celebrate the 50th anniversary of the first sub-Saharan country to gain independence. On *pronouns*, he uses the word "we" to interact with his audience and further his government's political agenda. The usage of the pronoun "we" is very significant because of its diversity from an analytical and sociological standpoint. According to Fairclough (2001, p. 106), there are inclusive "we" and exclusive "we". An inclusive "we" means that the writer or speaker is including the audience to whom he is speaking to, thereby uniting himself with them and creating a sense of a common purpose, while the exclusive "we" is when the writer or speaker is addressing one or more persons but not including the addressee(s). He uses the pronoun "we" three times in his press briefing, always in the same manner by using it to represent "we" the (NPP) government. He uses the exclusive "we" to refer to his government in the following expressions: "If we have money, we should think big and undertake projects which will become great landmarks" and "We have tried not to make the celebration partisan but a national one which will encompass all". Here one could see that he is speaking on behalf of the NPP government and this type "we" he uses to stress his government's agenda for the celebration and highlights what his government intends to do towards the 50th Independence anniversary celebration.

This in all probability, makes it clear that ruling the government has its own political agenda over the impending 50th Independence anniversary celebration. Once again, it could be argued that this graphical representation enacts unequal power relations in the sentences and also draw upon the ideological square, depicting the opposition as *outsiders* who should not, implicitly, be part of NPP government's agenda for the celebration and emphasising their negative characteristics while foregrounding *our* positive characteristics.

News Article 3: Unsavoury remarks about Presidency: IT'S TOTALLY UNACCEPTABLE, says Prez Kufuor. (Daily Graphic, Saturday, March 19, 2005. Pages 1 and 3)

On Friday, March 18, 2005, President Kufuor made this remark when a high-powered delegation from the Presbyterian Church of Ghana (PCG), paid a courtesy call on him at the Christiansburg Castle (also known as Osu Castle) to introduce the new Moderator of the church, Rt. Rev Dr Yaw Frimpong-Manso to him and also to congratulate him on his re-elections for another four-year term. The event which was covered and written by journalist Nehemia Owusu Achiaw, as a news article, appeared in the Daily Graphic on Saturday, March 19,

2005 with the above caption. His audience were the religious bodies and Ghanaians in general, irrespective of religious and socio-political background.

It was during this courtesy call, that the president took the opportunity to draw attention to the customary Ghanaian traditional practise where subjects accord respect to people in authority and called on all the religious, traditional and community leaders to come out to speak against any derogatory remarks by political leaders against people in authority. President Kufour's request was in reaction to remarks made by some leaders of a pressure group called "Wahala Two" which had staged a demonstration on Thursday, March 17, 2005, to voice their displeasure about the general economic hardship and the rise in petroleum prices existing under his rule. "Wahala" in the Ghanaian Language means 'trouble' or 'hardships' and that particular one (demonstration), was the second to drum home to the government the social and economic hardships the citizens are going through. Among the leaders of the demonstration was the former President Rawlings.

According to some news reports concerning the Wahala Two, former President Rawlings was chanting slogans like: "Kufuor nie, Ataa Ayi nie; Kufuor nie, Ewi nie" and "Kufuor nie, Ya-Na ti nie" – metaphorical statements to indicate that President Kufuor was a thief who had stolen state properties and assets and equated him to having the same qualities as a notorious armed robber and a thief Ata Ayi who had been arrested by the police in a fortnight before for armed robbery offences. "Kufuor nie, Ya-Na ti nie" also referred to Kufuor as a murderer of Ya-Naa Yakubu Andani II, the Overlord of Dagbon, March 25th to 27th, 2002, in Yendi in the Northern Region of Ghana. The call by the President on the religious, traditional and community leaders to come out and speak against any derogatory remarks by political leaders when the PCG delegation paid a courtesy call on him paid off. Within a couple of days after the visit, the clergy in Ghana issued a Pastoral Letter urging Rawlings to apologise. This call appeared on the Saturday, April 9, 2005 edition of the Daily Graphic as a news article.

Notwithstanding the call, the imputation of the opposition NDC was that the religious bodies were playing a central role in the reproduction of the dominant ideology between the ruling NPP and NDC. Again, they explained that because Kufuor was an Ashanti and a kinsman, that was why they were showing evidences of a systematic *othering* and *stereotyping* between Kufuor and Rawlings. Their (NDC) was that President Kufuor did the same thing when in opposition and even when he became President in 2001. For example, when he described former President Rawlings and his government in 2002 as evil forces during a GIMPA Workshop for NPP Ministers; and nothing was heard from them.

But in contrast to the other articles, this draws on a different ideological discourse. As an overall defining characteristic of the text, it should be outlined that while it exhibits the features of the ideological square and reflects on *Us* and *Them* power relations, the main emphasis is on negotiation rather than conflict and the predominant discourse here is *solidarity* and *mutuality*. Since the text accentuates *commonality* rather than *difference*, we shall first consider this tendency in the text. The most illustrative of this accentuation is the following paragraph: "Some political leaders might not like a person but once such a person is elected President, it is important for all citizens to accord him the necessary respect without which the high office of the land would be undermined and demeaned." The analogy is that, no matter how ordinary an individual may be, whenever the same person assumes a political position like the president of the state, the citizens accord that individual much respect because of the high office that the person now occupies. This analogy is particularly striking since it is the president of the country saying it through the voice of a state journalist; it could be argued that this account contributes to a certain *personification* of the text. Thus, creating a personal connection with the situation by drawing on identification. This is in line with Halliday's (1994) concept of *relational attributive processes*, in this case, the assignment of positive attributes to *Them*, simultaneously assumes the implicitness of *Us*, which serves to bridge the ideological gap and bracketing the differences. This could also be related to Fairclough's understanding of orientation of texts to difference, according to which, difference could be viewed in terms of a *bracketing of difference* and a *focus of commonality*. It is also noteworthy that the expression

“political leaders who make derogatory remarks about the presidency [...] such actions could turn the country’s liberalism into chaos” is de-constructing Van Dijk’s ideological matrix and inclining towards *positive other-presentation*. This is so because the remarks made were for the whole institution, the presidency or the high office of the land, not for a particular or a single president.

Likewise, the expression “He called on religious, traditional and community leaders to come out to speak against any derogatory remarks by political leaders” emphasises solidarity and mutuality as a key to consensus (normalisation and acceptance of differences of power) and promotes the possibility of meaningful socio-political change; meaning that by accentuating commonality, one simultaneously suppresses differences between *Us* and *Them*. Although the *Us* and *Them* power relations are still very relevant in the discursive framework of the text; nonetheless, the ideological conflict as such is not central, and instead, negotiation is paramount. Throughout the text, negotiation is enacted and represented by the interplay of statements or remarks by the president, emphasising both negative and positive other-presentation. which are predominantly positive self-presentation. This negotiation is achieved through the order and structuring of clauses and paragraphs. which in effect, reflect higher-level of semantic relations in the text, thus playing with relations of equivalence and difference. For instances, the remarks “We need to move forward as a nation...” was reasonably well expressed. This is to urge the citizens of Ghana, irrespective of their political background, to understand that politics of revenge and retaliation could only lead to national ruin and must therefore be avoided by leaving the past behind and focus on a bright future.

As emphasised previously, another defining characteristics of the text is its inclination towards solidarity and commonality. This is especially illuminated in remarks like “the country has reached a stage where its citizens should be single-minded in its development” and “since Ghanaians and not strangers had the onerous responsibility to build the country.” Here too, the discourse of solidarity is built upon the phrases “single-minded” and “Ghanaians,” a discourse which neither eliminates nor equalises on *Us* and *Them* power relations but merely acknowledges the possibility and the potential of positive other-presentation. Hence, it could be argued that the *Us* and *Them* power relations exist in this solidarity discourse but only to a degree where they contribute to consensus, defined by Fairclough as normalisation and acceptance of difference of power. In general, the text reports wider social and structural inequalities as well as reflects unequal power relations. At the same time, it draws on a different discourse (the negotiation discourse), accepting the possibility of a meaningful socio-political change and presenting discrimination (*othering*) and dominance (*hegemony*) as inhibiting multi-vocality.

News Article 4:5 To refund GHcedis 94, 080 (Daily Graphic, Thursday, May 13, 2010, pp. 1, 16/49)

President Atta Mills and his NDC were in power after the December 2008 presidential and parliamentary elections and as it has become the stock-in-trade for both the NDC and NPP whenever there is a swing of political pendulum to vilify and represent the *Other* (the party in opposition) negatively to reinforce the ideological separation between *Us* and *Them*, a request was made by the Office of the President through a letter dated March 29, 2010, to the Auditor-General (A-G). The letter requested the A-G to conduct an audit verification of Emoluments for Ex-Ministers and Members of Parliament (MPs) in order to advise on whether there were shortfalls in payments made by the Office of the President, there were any over-payments by Parliament and whether there was a basis for reconciliation of the various payments. On Thursday, May 13, 2010, the Daily Graphic newspaper carried the story written by Timothy Gobah, carrying the above headline. This headline was a directive by the A-G following his Report on the Verification of Payments of emoluments for ex-ministers and MPs.

This request by the Office of the President is a political tactic by the new NDC President to hide behind the A-G to perform its domestic political and ideological functions. It is also a way to appeal to the Ghanaian electorates and audience’s notion of truth and logic that there were lots of malfeasances during former President

Kufuor's administration. Again, the action proved that there were improprieties or over-payments made to four (4) ex-ministers in Kufuor's administration and a top NPP member who is now a Minority Leader in parliament. It is also an indication that the Mills administration was prudent in the administration and that it believes in accountability and probity. As a result, the five (5) named individuals will have to refund the said amount (GH cedis 94,080) as directed by the A-G. While it is appropriate and common practice for the new president to seek clarification on misappropriation of any funds, the nature of the request however- choosing the four NPP members, made it selective. As a result, the move can be interpreted to mean that the president was seeking to cause disaffection for the opposition NPP members among Ghanaians.

Secondly, the A-G was given a clear and specific assignment "to conduct an audit verification of Emoluments for Ex-Ministers and MPs to advise...." The catch word here is "to advise". Why then did the A-G "order" the 5 people to refund the amount? The possible answer is because the Office of the President did not want the Ghanaian audience and citizens to know explicitly that it is after the party in opposition. Thus, it uses behind-the-scene tactics (implicitly) and draws the A-G to do its dirty work for them in order to achieve an aim: *negative other-presentation*. So, the government is actually abusing its newly won power through manipulations while at the same time suppressing and de-emphasising information that is positive about *Them*. Practically, the A-G is always involved in malpractices and auditing of emoluments, ex-gratia and other payments in the country as an independent civil servant, not as a partisan political personality, but the vice versa is what happens whenever there is a swing of political pendulum. Hence, it could be argued that the text reports on wider social inequalities and unequal power relations occur whenever one political party is in power. Another way to understand how the "ideological square which depicts the party in opposition as outsiders could be seen is how Osei Kyei-Mensah and the four ex-ministers-all NPP members were singled out to refund the overpayment in their ex-gratia. This application highlights the negative characteristics of the opposition party. For example, as corrupt and only interested in over-paying their ministers and MPs when they were in power; while foregrounding *our* positive characteristics as a government who believes in accountability and probity and will make the those cited for over-payment refund what they were not supposed to be paid during the time their party was in power. Again, one could see and identify unequal power relations tactics being used by the Office of the President through the A-G in their pursuit to reflect on *Us* and *Them* power struggle in the text. An example can be seen from this sentence: "Four ex-ministers in the Kufuor administration and the current Minority Leader in Parliament, Mr. Osei Kyei-Mensah-Bonsu, have been ordered to refund a total of Ghana cedis 94,080 as overpayment made to them in their ex-gratia computation." As one of the opening paragraphs, this sentence immediately establishes a certain mood, representing the A-G as an institutional agent and drawing on *relational attributive processes* by assigning *authority* (agentive) attributes to the A-G (based on the request from the Office of the President) who ordered or directed the "5 To refund GHcedis 94,080."

Here, *positive self-presentation* is promoted by among others, employing *referential strategies* (Reisigl and Wodak, 2001) and contrasting the specific A-G directives. In this context, "ordered to refund" is used metaphorically to imply that (though implicitly) there were overpayments made to ministers and NPP functionaries during President Kufuor's administration and they have been detected after the audit verification conducted by the A-G based on request made to him/her by the Office of the President and the 5 will refund the overpaid amount, thus emphasising the *Us* and *Them* polarisation. The word "refund" used in the A-G's directive received lot of criticisms and reactions from the party in opposition members in the public sphere, especially in the private newspaper although the Daily Graphic newspaper gave a voice to the opposition which appeared as a reaction on Friday, May 21, 2010 though not as the speaking voice as the party in power. In a reaction to the A-G's findings, Mr. Osei Kyei-Mensah-Bonsu (who was reacting on behalf of his party, the NPP) expressed surprise how the affected persons were all NPP members) added "We will react appropriately when the details are made available to us." He further explained that "The purpose of this prank is obvious but this cannot intimidate us" and we will "challenge the government to cause the publication of the amount paid as ex-gratia to each former MP from both sides of the House."

Inter-textuality can be observed in political news articles. In this case, the A-G's directive ordering the 5 to refund the overpaid ex-gratia may create some sort of ambivalence to the open-minded audience who is not aware of and does not understand the original use. An instance can be drawn from a section in the news article: "Four ex-ministers in the Kufuor administration and the current Minority Leader in Parliament, Mr. Osei Kyei-Mensah-Bonsu, have been ordered to refund". In the above instance, no mark of partisan directive is used, but the Auditor-General's use of "refund" is part of a news discourse which creates more subtlety to the open-minded Ghanaian audience and a lot of excitement to the party in power's discourse community. The politically manipulation tone of *negative other-representation*, thus illuminating unequal power relations, is clearly evident and the members of the new government of the NDC discourse community have no problem understanding what is going on and its political implications for the opposition.

Regarding ideological square, the president and his NDC government (including its MPs and ex-ministers) are represented in a positive way by emphasising and thus, foregrounding *Our* positive characteristics – that neither our ex-ministers nor MPs were not over-paid so they are not being ordered to refund any amount by the A-G. This could be related to Halliday's perception of "actional processes," according to which the *negative other-presentation* can be indicated by a display of what *they* are doing with direct negative effect on *us*. In this case, it could be argued that the over-payment made to the 4 ex-ministers and the Minority Leader, all members of NPP, endangers *our* responsibility and ability as a new government to have the needed cash flow to solve economic and social problems. The Office of the President used the word "request" which can be a noun or verb. However, the motivation or intention behind the 'requests' thrusts us into believing that there is political undertone in the request. It points out we (us) are good and them are bad for stealing or depriving the state and the citizens of needed funds for development. In the context of the political news article, it is being used in explicitly, politely and formally to ask the A-G by a letter dated March 29, 2010: "requesting the Auditor-General to conduct an audit verification of Emoluments for Ex-Ministers and MPs to advise..." in an explicit manner. On that basis, it could be argued that this representation enacts unequal power relations in the news article and also draws upon the ideological square depicting *Them* the opposition as *outsiders* who should be blamed, explicitly, as national-coffer-plunders after the audit verification by the A-G.

News Article 5: Mills' Govt Saves GHcedis 8 million annually (Daily Graphic, Monday, June 7, 2010, pp. 1 and 3)

The above statement was made during an exclusive interview by the NDC Deputy Minister of Information (DMoI), Mr. Samuel Okudzeto Ablakwa with a state reporter, Timothy Gobah, on Sunday, June 6, 2010, which appeared as a written article on Monday, June 7, 2010, edition of the Daily Graphic newspaper to outline the government's achievements so far. In fairness, members of the party in opposition could also appear in similar exclusive interviews in the state-owned newspaper, but the reality is that, they would not be given the same speaking space as the party in power. The interview was directed at the Ghanaian audience and the Ghanaian electorate. In the interview, the DMoI was quoted by the state reporter as saying: "the government has, for the first time, quantified the savings that have accrued since President Mills began implementing a series of prudent and cost-saving measures, having campaigned vigorously to eliminate profligate expenditure from public administration." First, no manifestation marks could be linked to the text, so the audience's knowledge of the DMoI's use of the above expression in the interview depends entirely on how the texts are produced and appeared in the news article. Second, the structure of the text is more like horizontal inter-textuality where the DMoI is taking turns in an interview (as an interviewee) previously started by an interviewer. It also emphasises "positive self-representation" of the new President Mills of the NDC and the *negative other-presentation* of the immediate past Kufuor's NPP government as reflected in the order of the first paragraph of the text and it is particularly noteworthy how the specific "President Mills" is drawn against the backdrop of "began implementing a series of prudent and cost-saving measures". Thereby explicitly presenting the new NDC

government of President Mills resolve to eliminate lavish spending and cut out waste as compared to the opposition NPP when they were in power.

The above could be related to Richardson's (2007, p. 49) understanding of media discourses as constitutive of certain social categories, by among others, choosing to "foreground one social category over other equally accurate alternatives". It can also be related to Halliday's idea of "participants" in terms of naming and referencing, according to which, participants represented by name could be seen as fore-grounded and promoted. Furthermore, in terms of van Dijk's ideological square, both President Mills and his NDC government are presented in a positive way by emphasising, and thus, foregrounding *our* positive characteristics. This can also be related to Halliday's perception of "actional processes" (which encapsulates both verbal and material processes), according to which, the *negative other-presentation* can be indicated by a display of what *they* are doing with a direct negative effect on *Us*. In this case, it could be seen from the DMOI's interview that because of lavish spending and profligate expenditure "associated" with former President Kufuor's government, prudent, cost-saving measures and waste were not adopted for public administration thereby preventing the development of the country. This clearly supports the notion of *Us* and *Them* ideological polarisation whenever, either, the NDC or the NPP is given the democratic mandate through general elections to rule.

The DMOI used the exclusive interview to recount the achievements within the 5 months of President Mills' government through prudent, cost-saving and the resolve of the President to cut waste as compared to the eight (8) years rule of former President Kufuor whose government indulged in lavish spend and encouraged profligate expenditure in public administration. Implicitly, he is playing on the logic understanding of his audience to see and appreciate the differences between *good* and *bad* government. This part of the text in the exclusive interview presupposes that of the eight (8) years that the opposition NPP was ruling Ghana, it never initiated and implemented any prudent and cost-saving measures to eliminate profligate expenditure from public administration, in other words, NPP only indulges in lavish spending and takes delight in creating projects that are detrimental to the development of the country. This epitomises *negative other-presentation* by the DMOI of the opposition NPP which is reflected in the interview. To support his argument in the interview, he quoted an example to buttress point: "He stated, for example, that if one compared the presidential delegation to the opening ceremonies of the 2006 World Cup and the 2010 World Cup, whereas President Kufuor travelled with a 35-member delegation, President Mills would travel with a 14-member delegation", this shows how President Mills is being represented in a *positive* by emphasising, and thus, foregrounding *his* positive characteristics and de-emphasising and suppressing information that is positive about President Kufuor.

Like all the articles, through the voice of the state reporter and to avoid the risk of being seen as aggressive, offensive towards and verbally attacking the party in opposition, the DMOI quoted in a skilful way to make him appear neutral and objective before the Ghanaian audience, hence giving the impression that he is talking about those things as facts when in fact, he is intentionally conveying the ruling NDC government's ideological message. Therefore, this kind of inter-textuality is not innocent politically as a news article because it hides implicit ideological meaning and it is this strategy, he used to save the face of President Mills' (NDC) government through alienating it from the proposition made originally in other news articles by the opposition NPP. This practice of the DMOI created some moral ambivalence because some of his audience interpreted them as a deliberate continuation of the *negative other-presentation*. This is so because it came at the backdrop of the 2008 elections where Ghanaians were calling for calm and unity and not the usual "good and bad government game" that has polarised and escalated hostilities between the ruling NDC government and the opposition NPP since 1992. But, for DMOI's discourse community, the quotation is what they needed to hear and appreciate so as to reinforce the unequal power relations; thus, his quotation is accepted by his audience as it corresponds to the *negative other-presentation* of the opposition NPP.

On the issue of “modality,” it is very significant to take note how the word *would* was used three times in the interview; it is a “modal verb” and according to Fairclough (2003a, p. 165) modality is an important dimension of applying discourse analysis, thus the modality of the DMoI’s expressions shows how much he is willing to commit himself to what he is expressing, i.e. the truth-value of his expressions (in epistemic modality). He uses a lot of categorical modalities and in doing so, he casts himself as someone who has the ability to predict the future for Mills’ government of which he himself is a member. As it can be seen in the following: “At this trend, he said, over four-year term, President Mills would have ensured a saving of Ghs 23,076,000” and “[...] “it would ensure that the benefits were channelled into the development of the country.” In using *would*, which is used as the past form of *will*, when reporting what the DMoI has said or thought, metaphorically, he was practically using Mills adjectively to make the differentiation clear and intentionally convey ideological messages of the ruling NDC; which is also (“Mills’ govt”) a context-bound, in the sense that, by using that he is referring to the opposition NPP and underlying personal attacks (all done implicitly though) on the opposition. On *verbs*, the use of the word “saves” which can be a verb, noun, preposition or conjunction, the DMoI uses the verb (and the synonym) form to interact with his audience in order to further his political agenda. By using the word “saves” eight (8) times over short period of the interview, he is stressing on the importance the Mills’ government attaches to implementing a series of prudent and cost-saving measures to eliminate profligate expenditure from public administration, though implicitly, as compared with the opposition NPP.

News Article 6: STX deal expected to create 40,000 jobs (Daily Graphic, Saturday, August 28, 2010. Page 19)

On Wednesday, August 25, 2010, the Minister of Water Resources and Housing (MoWRaH) of the ruling NDC, Mr. Alban Bagbin, paid a visit to the personnel of Ghana Prisons Service in a durbar at Accra to explain the STX housing project in detail to them. Prior to this, he had already interacted with the Military, Police and the Ghana National Fire Service personnel because under the project, 30,000 housing units were expected to be constructed for the security agencies across the country. It was at the durbar that he announced the STX deal is expected to create over 40,000 jobs with the establishment of major cement, steel and power plants in the country. The importance of his visit was to help the beneficiaries of the project appreciate and support what the ministry was bringing to their doorsteps. He therefore appealed for co-operation and support of the security personnel to ensure the smooth take-off of the project and warned that structures like markets and churches on the lands which had been earmarked for the construction of the units would be demolished.

Although one can clearly see how he is using manipulation as a discursive social practice of the ruling NDC towards the reproduction of its power through persuasion, education and providing information that out of the 30,000 houses to be built for the security agencies, 4,000 would be allocated to Prison Services; it was all aimed at influencing, implicitly, their knowledge and beliefs about the deal in order to win the support of the security agencies. This supports the argument that in Ghanaian politics, national developmental projects, such as the STX housing project, are always politicised and polarised on party lines. But as in article three, there is an inclination towards solidarity and commonality permeating through the text. This is explicitly noticed in the remarks by the MoWRaH in his interaction with the personnel of the Ghana Prisons Service that: “all housing projects started by the previous administration would be continued.” This statement (if sincere) is a landmark in the political history of Ghana because no government either democratically elected or military dictatorship, had openly stated the continuation of a project that has been started by its predecessor.

So, for an NDC ranking member and a minister to utter such a statement, shows a clear change of political paradigm. This can be used to buttress the shifting political paradigm in relation to accentuating commonality and de-accentuating differences between the two political parties which have taken turns to rule Ghana. This makes one to say that the tendencies detected in the article presuppose that there is acceptance of the possibility of a meaningful social change by the political parties, especially, the NDC and NPP.

Conclusion(s)

To operationalise and epitomise the authors' case study, six (6) news articles of political nature were selected from the Daily Graphic and analysed. The authors discovered that a sentence or an expression is worded or constructed linguistically, has an important impact on its message and the perception of the message in a political setting. Thus, in Ghana politics the representation of the 'Other' in political news discourses on not explicitly polarised issues, reflects a clear differentiation between *Us* (the parties in power) and *Them* (the parties in opposition) and these differentiations are clear in texts through *positive self-presentation* and *negative other-presentation*. Hence, the authors concluded that the texts published by the state-owned Daily Graphic as political news articles (in four (4) out of the 6 articles selected – article 1, 2, 4 and 5 specifically) not only indicate or reflect unequal power relations, but they also reflect wider social, cultural, structural and ideological inequalities.

It was also discovered that ideological biases were linguistically embedded in the written reports of the party in power in the Daily Graphic newspaper. Thus, supporting the assumption that the state-owned media provide a perspective, i.e., far from free subjective interpretation of events in Ghana politics. On the contrary, it tends to construct reality in a manner congruent with its underlying ideological and political functions. Based on these discoveries, the authors concluded that the state-owned media discourses were biased, skewed in favour of the parties in power (and it changes whenever there is a swing of political pendulum), and even when the parties in opposition were given voice, they were not given the same speaking space. Hence, revealing asymmetrical reproduction of unequal power relations between political parties and the operation of *Us* and *Them* framework by the state-owned newspaper when reporting political news events in Ghana.

The identification of unequal power relations in the texts is particularly evident when one applies van Dijk's (1995, p. 1998) notion of ideological square which is characterised by *positive in-group* and *negative out-group* description. This ideological square provided a reasonable explanation for the analysis and discussion. Van Dijk maintains that many group ideologies involve the representation of *self* and *other* and *us* and *them*. Many therefore seem to be polarised – We are *good* and they are *Bad*, and the ideological square functions to polarise *in-and-out groups* in order to present the, *we* group in a favourable light and the, *they* group unfavourably. This ideological polarisation may be implemented by a larger variety of forms such as choice of lexical items that imply positive or negative evaluations, as well as in the structure of whole propositions and their categories – as in active, passive, etc. Thus, looking at the textual elements in terms of *positive self-presentation* and *negative other-presentation*, as well as identifying types of meanings as enacted in textual features based on Halliday's framework of processes, participants and circumstances and on Fairclough's understanding of action, representation and identification, it was concluded on the basis of a systematic and thorough analysis of the articles that the texts in the Daily Graphic newspaper articles overwhelmingly draw on the ideological square paradigm; emphasising the *Us* and *Them* polarisation in political news discourses.

Additionally, it was concluded that political leaders in Ghana, taking into consideration how different people interact with political news discourses, exploit readers of the Daily Graphic newspaper political discourses through the voices of state journalists whenever one party is in power. Most of the exploitations were in relation to the representation of the 'Other' which has the functions of criticising or blaming, either explicitly or implicitly, the party in opposition's inter-texts. At the manifest level, prior texts of the party in opposition were referred to in a form of quotations. This type of inter-textuality is supposed to be an innocent practice whose purpose was to view the topic in question objectively from 'others' perspective to avoid plagiarism. However, the analysis revealed that the inter-text used by the politicians, both manifest and constitutive, were misleading. This occurred when the politician in question used the text to express a negative idea about the party in opposition and its leaders by selecting quotations that served his/her domestic and ideological purposes. This was because by quoting, (the politician) attacked the party in opposition and its leaders which appeared in

the Daily Graphic newspaper through the voice of state journalists without the politician having to bear the responsibility as he/she can always claim that he/she was quoting or merely quoting an opposition member to buttress a point. In a Ghanaian political context, even the most neutral way of manifesting inter-textuality, i.e., quotations, proved to mark an attack on the party in opposition without explicitly appearing to do so. Additionally, the authors discovered that Ghanaian politicians used expressions that were constructed to be direct and straight-forward with little use of euphemistic language or agentless passives, although there were a few exceptions. Rather, they tend to use categorical modality extensively indicating that they attach a strong truth-value to the statements.

These along with the fact that they mostly make demands, not request, making them as politicians who were not in position of power, but who were willing to make them also believe in the righteousness of the ideologies and political cause. Also, the political parties use hyperboles in their discourses based on what they were achieving when in power rather than what their opponents or detractors were saying. Based on this, it was concluded that political news articles written by state journalists that appeared in the Daily Graphic newspaper were part of the struggle for hegemony that Fairclough describes as “creating the world in their own political image” by the political parties in Ghana. Furthermore, it is important to emphasise that the notion of social change was not one of the main focuses of the study, but the idea of an openness towards a meaningful socio-political change was evident in the texts, thus reflecting a bottom-up approach, rather than defined or pointed out as an analytical dimension prior to the analysis and discussion. This was so because some of the texts draw on slightly different discursive tendencies, crystallised in Fairclough’s approaches to differences and commonality, which aims at bridging the *Us* and *Them* polarisation and accentuating negotiating rather than conflict; commonality rather than difference and equality rather than inequality. Moreover, tendencies were also detected in the 6 selected articles (refer to article 3 and 6) towards accepting the possibility of a meaningful social change and presenting ‘*Othering*,’ manipulation and dominance/hegemony (and social inequalities in general) as thwarting multi-vocality and socio-political dynamism. On the basis of these findings, the authors concluded that as a reflection on the process of the analysis, it is crucial to note that the evidences extracted from some of texts in article 3 and 6 seem, in some instances, to be in balance in the findings which supported and contradicted the authors initial assumptions when analysed and discussed, thus equally enriching the analysis.

Finally, based on the case study which resulted in the analysis of 6 selected political news articles published by the state-owned Daily Graphic newspaper from 2005 to 2010, it can be considered as an ‘*alternative*’ setting to subject matters usually investigated by CDA; not only because it diverged from issues typically addressed by CDA, but also because in the articles analysed, unequal power struggle was the main theme and the underlining subject matter that framed the events represented in the texts. Thus, it was noticed from the articles analysed and discussed that unequal power relations were maintained in political news discourses in the Daily Graphic newspaper on not explicitly polarised issues. Hence, it could therefore be concluded that CDA can be practically and productively applied to ‘*alternative*’ setting, as well as the scope of issues addressed by CDA can be broadened to include not explicitly polarised issues. Because, the analysis of the articles pointed to the fact that unequal power relations and the polarisation between *Us* and *Them* in political news discourses, were not associated only with the contexts in which there was an explicit conflict between different political parties. Rather, it pointed to more pervasive phenomena and ideological differences in which parties in opposition were presented negatively as the ‘*Other*’ in political discourses.

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